

Mobile robot localization and path planning based on Feature recognition and Dijkstra's Algorithm

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Abstract: This paper proposes a fast localization method, based on a simple feature recognition like a sphere. The local and the global position obtained by scenario reconstruction, and feature recognition as the reference for localization. A 2D laser range finder mounted on a tilting mechanism scans the 3D information of the environment. The 3D workspace divided by triangulation, and a path planned for fast obstacle avoidance created by connecting the center points of each of the generated tetrahedron using Dijkstra's algorithm.

Keywords: Mobile robot, path planning, obstacle avoidance, feature recognition, 3D mapping.

1. INTRODUCTION

Localization is one of the most critical challenges in the research of mobile robot. Several algorithms tackle this problem recreating 2D or 3D maps, using a Lidar sensor have been developed to avoid obstacles and model the workspace for path planning. The scan-matching concept is highly applicable for localization and map building problems for a 2D workspace, among them most typical applications are the automatic cleaners and grass choppers. The SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping), proposes the robot localization in an unknown environment, using simple features as reference points. The algorithm proclaims the use of a mathematical model for the localization, and later on, dispose of all the references obtained to create a map for the robot.

For robot path planning, one of the standard solutions in 2D and 3D is the Iterative Closest Point algorithm (ICP), which is highly dependable on the information provided by the laser sensor. Moreover, due the processing time of the entire point cloud, requires a big amount of effort and it is time demanding. The proposing method in this paper consists of processing the whole point cloud, just for just identifying a single reference object, for this case a sphere, and from it obtain the current localization of the robot combining respectively with the information provided by the odometry sensors. Most of the previous researchers have used the scan matching technique [1-4], for localization. Scan matching recognizes features from the scanned data by a laser sensor and proceeds the data with geometric operations, using triangulations as line fitting and split and merge algorithm, the points in the scan data is divided, once completed, it goes through a cell decomposition for localization, distributing all the range of interest.

Considering the several approximations for the simultaneous mapping and localization (SLAM) as in [5-7], applied to indoor environments, this method requires the sensor odometry information and combining the signal using the Kalman Filter. Also as it could involve

using histograms recording the measures from the laser scans [8], later on, are probabilistic approximation models [9] processing data obtained from feature extraction, conducting this could achieved a consistent range of scan mapping [10]. In the case of the point cloud generation based on the 2D sensor with a tilting mechanism, there are couple methods as it is described on [13-15, 18] an accurate 2D data acquisition is shown and converted in a 3D point cloud. The Voronoi Diagram used in mobile robotics as in [25], and also some algorithms using the optimization theory as is shown on [28]. As well the decomposition of geometric figures analyzed for the planning motion [29, 30], and there are attempts to use the Voronoi Diagram in 3D dimension as is shown in [32].

With all of those efforts, is evidence that the computational geometry algorithms used for applications in mobile robotics. Even though the idea of combining the information from a point cloud and using for reconstructing a scenario on 3D, it is a brand new concept and the purpose of the current work is to demonstrate through a simulation the veracity of it.

2. POINT CLOUD GENERATION

For the experiment procedure, a solid sphere made of rubber, located in one hall. The sphere should be in the around the corner area, to obtaining better results on the plane reconstruction. Moreover, the detection of the walls and the floor rely on the information provided by the Point Cloud. The Dimensions of the scenario are specified by the Figure 1.

Item	Distance (m)
a.	2.5
b.	2.5
c.	2.0
d.	0.4
e.	1.4

Figure 1. Scenario dimension.

A Kobuki robot used to perform the experiment, provided by a Lidar Sensor Hokuyo URG-04LX Laser, this sensor combined with a tilting mechanism generates a 3D point Cloud. The information collected is extensive and requires a filter to reduce the size of the point cloud. For it was used a simple technique, determining the range of interest (ROI) extracting the sphere and every wall plane points.

a) Kobuki Robot.

b) Tilting Mechanism.

Figure 2. Kobuki robot provided by a Laser sensor and Tilting Mechanism.

3. EXPERTIMENT AND RESULTS

The algorithm follows the next steps:

Figure 3. Kobuli robot provided by a Laser sensor and Tilting Mechanism,

For processing the point cloud, and generate the scenario information, the robot reconstructs a new system coordinate and using it as a reference for the new measurements. Therefore, the Point Cloud will be divided into three planes using the singular value decomposition.

Figure 4. Plane extraction from the point cloud using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD).

Once the reconstruction on the scenario is complete, the Delaunay triangulation applied over it, identifying the corner points of every plane, and the number of tetrahedrons, the next step is connecting all the tetrahedrons center points.

a) 3D Scenario Model.

b) Localizing center point in every tetrahedrons.

Figure 5. 3D reconstruction of the experiment scenario

The following step generates the optimal path, on the connected the points, first localizing the critical edges and then avoiding the sphere obstacle ROI, the optimal path obtained using the Dijkstra's algorithm.

a) Scenario Triangulated and center points connected.

b) Dijkstra's Algorithm diagram

Figure 6. Scenario Triangulation

Finally, the path obtained from the 3D space, let the robot move forward and avoid sphere obstacle, using only the information from the one point cloud.

a) Dijkstra algorithm apply on the critical edges

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